

PREFORMING OF FIBRE BRIDGING FOR IMPROVED DAMAGE TOLERANCE

P. Potluri*, M Arshad, D. Jetavat, P. Jamshidi, P. Hogg
 School of Materials, University of Manchester, M13 9PL, UK
 * Corresponding author (prasad.potluri@manchester.ac.uk)

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Abstract

This paper presents various manufacturing schemes for creating through-thickness reinforcement including stitching, tufting and 3D weaving. 3D weaves are promising for improving damage tolerance over large areas, where as stitching and tufting are suitable for local reinforcement. Several 3D woven architectures have been produced and evaluated for damage tolerance.

1 Introduction

With the increasing use of advanced composites in aircraft primary structures, damage tolerance has received attention in recent years. Amongst various toughening schemes, inter-laminar fibre-bridging is considered to be the most effective method in improving the damage tolerance. This paper reviews various manufacturing techniques for creating fibre-bridging with a view to understand the influence of fibre architecture on mechanical properties.

The need for damage tolerant composites transcends all parts of the composites industry common to structures made from carbon or glass fibres for applications in aerospace to marine and wind turbines. Perhaps the most high profile and historically most critical applications have been carbon fiber composites in primary aerospace structures. Here the problem of damage is compounded by the fact that damage is commonly sub-surface, undetectable by eye, but can have a considerable detrimental effect on key laminate properties such as compression after impact. The importance of damage tolerance in the aerospace sector is increasing given the trend to manufacture more primary civil aircraft structures from CFRP, including the fuselage which is susceptible to significant airfield abuse (baggage handling, vehicles etc) and from large hail stones. However

damage tolerance in general is also of prime concern to the wind turbine industry as it is simply not economic to replace damaged blades in service, especially if the turbines are deployed off-shore.

The industry has made considerable progress for a thirty year time period in improving the damage tolerance of all classes of composites. This is exemplified by the improvements in carbon fiber composites intended for service as primary structures in aerospace where the damage tolerance of the composite laminate is usually quantified by measuring the compression after impact strength according to some recognized standard. Low energy impact is a significant in-service problem which results in difficult to detect damage, primarily consisting of delaminations, which can seriously reduce the compression strength of a composite laminate.

The compression after impact properties have increased when measured using the Boeing standard test method from a level of about 170 MPa to almost 400 MPa in this period. The improvements have been largely the result of increases in resin toughness leading to inter-laminar shear strength. The developments have included the introduction of formulated epoxies, followed by rubber toughened systems, thermoplastic toughened systems, through to thermoplastic, phase inverted thermoplastic-epoxies, monolithic thermoplastics and interleaf toughened epoxies. It is noticeable however that no significant improvements in damage tolerance have been developed over the last ten years, possibly as no specific new targets have been set by the industry. Boeing had stipulated a challenging CAI value of 350 MPa for selection of prepreg systems for use on the Boeing 777 empennage which was achieved. Most development work undertaken recently by industry has focused on developing composite systems (materials and preforms) that can

be used in alternative out-of-autoclave processes to deliver equivalent damage tolerance to conventional autoclave processed materials. It might be concluded that the process of achieving increased toughness via improvements in resin toughening have reached the end of its life and that there is little room for further development. If this is indeed the case then alternative strategies for developing an enhanced damage tolerance must be considered. In aerospace, the desirability of developing a carbon fiber fuselage for medium size single aisle commercial aircraft, when the fuselage thickness is very low, means that composite systems with a damage tolerance substantially above the level achieved to date are required. While the fuselage of a large twin aisle aircraft is tough enough to withstand damage from hail stones, service abuse etc, a thinner single aisle aircraft would not be capable of safe operation. If the resin toughening schemes have reached a limit, then modifying fibre architectures is the remaining option for further improvement to damage tolerance.

2 Manufacturing techniques

3D weaving has been considered as a prime candidate for creating inter-laminar fibre bridging. Fibre architectures include through-thickness weaves such as orthogonal, layer-to-layer and angle interlock weaves (figure.1). These 3D preforms are relatively easy to produce on electronic Jacquard looms.

Figure 1: 3D woven structures

Stitching of 2D plies is another flexible technique for through thickness reinforcement. Individual 2D plies are cut to the required size and orientation (using a ply cutter) and stacked together to create a ply layout. These plies are then stitched together to create a preform with through-thickness reinforcement. Conventional single needle stitching is a relatively slow process. A multi-needle stitching facility (figure 2) has been developed to improve the

throughput. This machine can stitch through a thick stack of fabrics using a row of needles (with each needle having a yarn supplied from a creel). Once the loops are formed, a rapier inserts a locking thread across. One disadvantage with this system is potential fibre damage or distortion during needle insertion.

Figure 2: multi-needle stitching

Tufting is another technique for through thickness reinforcement. Tufting does not require a locking thread and hence a simpler process in comparison to stitching. Dell'Anno et al [1] studied tufting extensively for improving damage tolerance. One limitation with tufting is that it leaves a resin rich layer on the loop side.

3. Impact Testing of 3D woven laminates

3D woven glass fibre laminates were produced with architectures including orthogonal, layer-to-layer, modified layer-to-layer and angle interlocked configurations, and infused with epoxy resin system.

3D weave Unidirectional
Figure 3: damage area in a 3D weave in comparison to Unidirectional laminate

Laminates were subjected to drop-weight test. Figure 3 compares the impact damage in a 3D woven laminate with a unidirectional 2D laminate. Impact damage area in all 3D woven laminates was significantly smaller than 2D laminates. Damage spreads in-plane along the fibre direction in traditional 2D laminates where as damage is concentrated in a circular region smaller than the indenter diameter.

Figure 4: Damage resistance of various architectures

Figure 4 presents the damage resistance for 3D woven laminates and compares the results with 2D laminates. Damage resistance is computed as the energy required for creating a unit area of damage [2]. Damage resistance of 3D woven laminates has been found to be significantly higher than 2D laminates. Ease of repair is another advantage of localised damage found in 3D laminates.

4. In-plane compression tests

In-plane compression tests were conducted on undamaged as well as damaged samples using a special fixture developed by Hogg [3] for thin samples. Samples tested in this work were less than 2mm in thickness and hence had a considerable problem of buckling.

Compression tests on undamaged samples (figure 5) showed some interesting differences between 3D woven and UD laminates. UD laminate failed instantly once the maximum stress is reached. On the other hand, 3D woven laminates exhibited a degree of plasticity beyond the point of peak stress; samples did not break completely but formed ‘plastic hinges.’ 2D woven laminates exhibited a degree of plasticity but the final failure is similar to that of a UD laminate.

Figure 5: compression stress-strain curves

Amongst 3D woven laminates, angle interlocked weave exhibited highest stiffness and strength due to relatively small waviness of the tows. Layer-to-layer weave has the highest tow waviness and as a result exhibited lowest compression strength and stiffness. Tow waviness angle is the primary factor influencing the compression strength of the laminates irrespective of weave style.

5. Compression after impact tests

Compression after impact tests were conducted on all laminates subjected to impact energy ranging from 5 to 30 J. CAI strength values as a function of impact energy levels are plotted in figure 6. There is a gradual reduction in compression strength with respect to the impact energy.

Figure 6: CAI versus impact energy

UD cross-ply has the highest undamaged strength followed by angle interlock weave; layer-to-layer weaves have the lowest compression strength due to tow waviness; orthogonal weave has median compression strength due to the presence of combination of stuffer and binder tows. Compression strength of a 2D woven laminate is closer to orthogonal weave. Rate of change of compression strength with respect to impact energy is somewhat similar for all four 3D weaves as well as the UD cross-ply. 2D woven laminate appears to have steeper reduction in compression strength with respect to impact energy.

Figure 7: Normalised compression strength versus damage width

Figure 7 presents normalised compression data (CAI values divided by undamaged compression strength) with respect to the damage width. Unlike 2D

weaves, compression strength doesnot degrade upto a certain damage size. There appears to be a ‘threshold’ damage size in 3D woven laminates. This suggests that small BVIDs (barely visible impact damage) are less likely to be detrimental in 3D woven laminates in comparison to 2D laminates.

Amongst the four weaves, angle interlock laminates appear to suffer the least damage and the modified layer-to-layer laminates suffer most damage.

6. Conclusion

3D woven composites exhibit significantly smaller damage area in comparison to 2D laminates; damage area is not strongly influenced by the weave style. Rate of change of CAI with respect to impact energy is also very similar for all four 3D weaves. Main difference appears to be the undamaged compression strength; undamaged compression strength decrease almost linearly with tow waviness angle. Weave parameters should be optimized in order to minimize tow waviness.

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